

A Study On The Impact Of Digitalisation Towards Cashless Economy In India

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ABSTRACT

Government of India had launched Digital India program with the aim of transforming the entire nation into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. Cashless, paperless economy is one of the perceived roles of Digital India movement. Different digital modes for financial payments are available still India continues to be driven by the utilization of money. Reason being there's nothing truly compete with the pliability of money. Government of India has taken initiatives to drive card transactions and cashless payments which posted healthy growth over the last couple of years subsequent to the government's demonetization initiative in November 2016. Although the expansion in mobile payments, card transactions continue to be the hugest driver of cashless payment transactions. In this article, an attempt has been made to study about digital transactions with cashless economy and expansion of digital transactions in India.

Keywords: Cashless Payment, Digital Transactions, Demonetization, Economy, Digital, Digitalisation

INTRODUCTION

India being a cash-intensive economy has a large percentage of transactions being carried out in cash due to poor digital literacy in the country. The last few years had been the year of major changes by Government of India through 'Digital India Campaign'. 'The Digital India program' is a flagship program of the Govt. of India with a vision to rework India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. Faceless, Paperless, Cashless is one among professed role of 'Digital India'. With the announcement of prime minister of India, on 8th November 2016, two of the largest denominations of currency notes of INR 500 and INR 1000 were demonetized with an immediate effect. The main aim behind this step was aimed to attack on black money, currency used for terrorist financing, black

money and corruption. Demonetization decision is a major driver for making India a cashless economy. Demonetization decision coupled with government's initiative to make India a cashless economy is expected to bring a phenomenal transformation in the way people make payments and expected to increase inclination towards online payment. Post demonetization, people gradually initiated embracing digital transactions and at the same time small business merchants and shop owners started receiving payments by means of digital mode. It was found that there is an increase in usage of digital transactions such as more credit and debit card transactions and mobile - wallets to make payments, after the implementation of demonetization In this research article we will have a detailed study about the upward trends of digital transactions with cashless economy, various types of digital payments in India and the prospects of cashless economy in India.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mr. Bharat Khurana (2015), Dream of cashless India: Benefits and challenges. The paper studies the benefits and challenges associated with India after becoming a cashless nation. It also helps in assessing the meaning of digital India and steps taken by government towards achieving the dream of cashless India. After the study no matter how much the government had done for fulfilling the dream of digital India but there is still a lot more that can be done to achieve that dream.

K. C. Balaji and K. Balaji (2016)"A Study on Demonetization and Its Impact on Cashless Transactions" considered that the development of the cashless exchange framework is achieving new statures. Individuals tend to move to cashless exchanges. It is on the right track to state that the cashless framework is a prerequisite as well as a requirement for the general public. However, then again, the danger of digital wrongdoing is especially higher as all the cashless exchanges are done over web. So appropriate and finish mindfulness must be made to the general population to keep their charge and Mastercards safe and to utilize the web saving money and the advanced wallet in a most secure manner. So as to rebuff the digital lawbreakers, the legitimately organized digital police compel with top of the line criminological labs and innovation must be made.

Mr. Pradeep H. Tawade (2017), “Future and scope of cashless economy in India.” This paper helps to assess the long run trends and therefore the after effect of going cashless within the Indian economic. It was seen that the Government of India should consider some more steps in digitalizing India by making the payment method secure and risk free.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY..

1. To study the different methods of digital payments in India.
2. To identify the factors promoting digital transaction System.
3. To study the upward trend of Cashless and Digital transactions in India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology involves specific techniques that are adopted in research process to collect assemble and evaluate data. It defines those tools that are used to gather relevant information in a specific research study.

This paper is a conceptual paper based on descriptive analysis using various secondary data and includes different literature reviews, published sources of data collected from various research papers and data from RBI website.

METHODS OF DIGITAL PAYMENTS IN INDIA:

- **Cards:** These includes the use of all types of plastic cards such as credit card, debit card, cash card, travel card etc. they provide 2 factor authentications for a secure transaction.
- **USSD:** Unstructured Supplementary Service Data is an innovative of making payments without the use of internet and smart phone. The payments can be made by a feature phone by dialing *99#.AEPS:

- **Aadhar Enabled Payment System** is a means by which a person can make payments at the point of sale by Aadhar authentication.
- **UPI:** Unified Payment Interface allows the user to link multiple bank accounts into a single mobile application, merging all or some of the banking services.
- **Mobile Wallets:** It is a means of carrying cash in digital format. Credit card or debit card can be linked to the mobile wallet for making payments or some money can be loaded into the mobile wallet.
- **Internet Banking:** It is a medium through which various banking services like NEFT, RTGS, ECS, IMPS etc. can be availed over the institution's website
- **Mobile Banking:** It is a service provided by banks providing its customers a platform to conduct various banking services by use of their mobile phones or tablets through the apps provided by the bank.

FACTORS PROMOTING CASHLESS TRANSACTION SYSTEM IN INDIA

- **Faster, convenient & ease of accessibility:** Customers need no longer to carry cash or visit an ATM. In fact, they don't even got to be physically present to pay Customers pays anytime from any a part of the planet. Digital, banking services are going to be available to customers on a 24/7 basis and on all days of a year, including bank holidays
- **Lower risk:** Digital transactions are far more secure than traditional transactions because they're processed by secure gateways which are hard to tamper with.
- **Easily traceable:** Details of payments are easily traceable in merchant-specific databases. Both merchants and customers have quick access to payment information. This avoids ambiguity and confusion while tracking payments.
- **Economical and fewer transaction fee:** There are many payment apps and mobile wallets that don't charge any quite service charge or processing fee for the service provided. The UPI interface is one such example, where the customer utilize the services free of cost. Various digital payments systems are bringing down costs.

- **Rewards, discounts and cash backs:** There are many rewards and discounts offered to customers using digital payment apps and mobile wallets. Attractive cash back, offers are given by many digital payment banks which comes as boon to customers and also acts an important factor to go cashless.
- **One stop solution for paying bills:** Many digital wallets and payment apps became a convenient platform for paying utility bills. Be it mobile bills, internet or electricity bills, all such utility bills are often paid through one app with none hassle.
- **Helps keep black money under control:** Digital transactions will help the govt keep a track of things and it'll help eliminate the circulation of black money and counterfeit notes in the long run. Apart from this, this might also provide a boost to the economy because the cost of minting currency

UPWARD TREND OF CASHLESS AND DIGITAL TRANSACTIONS IN INDIA

Digital payments are slowly gaining popularity in India and there are many apps that are being launched in this sector. It has become a hassle-free and secure way to make payments. The table below shows numbers of transactions through different digital platforms in India over past 3 financial years.

Year	No. of transactions (in Millions)					
	RTGS	NEFT	Credit Card	Debit Card	POS	UPI
2016-17	107.80	1,622.10	1,087.10	2,399.30	378.78	17.90
2017-18	124.40	1,946.40	1,405.20	3,343.40	446.19	915.20
2018-19	136.60	2,318.90	1,762.60	4,414.30	569.98	5,353.40

From the above table and chart it is inferred that there is a gradual increase in the usage of cashless and digital platform for making transactions by the people of India.

CONCLUSION

It can be predicted that in forthcoming years there will be a sharp and unexpected rise in the number of digital payment transactions in India. The digital payments sector i.e., cashless payments transactions will cross 1 trillion in succeeding 5 years. UPI and Aadhaar will help increase digital penetration, consistent with sources. UPI fund transfer money can be sent using a virtual address without providing IFSC code or account number. The usage of UPI continues to grow exponentially touching 5 billion in the coming years.

There is still a lack of trust and confidence among people while using digital payment methods. A lot of development in the field of infrastructure is required to make the dream of Digital India a reality. There are a lot of challenges in fulfilling the dream of digital India but in the long run cashless economy will help in growth and will bring a lot of benefits and opportunities with it.

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